

Sympatric occurrence of three colour morphs of the Common Egg-eater *Dasypeltis scabra* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Squamata: Colubridae) in central South Africa

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ABSTRACT

We report on the sympatric occurrence of three colour pattern morphs of the Common Egg-eater *Dasypeltis scabra* at a single locality in the northern Free State Province, central South Africa: typically patterned morph (grey-brown with dark brown vertebral saddles and lateral bars), ‘plain’ morph (brown with a dark vertebral stripe) and intermediate morph (brown, weakly and partially patterned with darker markings). In South Africa, patterned and ‘plain’ morphs are known to occur sympatrically in Highveld grassland areas in the central and northern Free State, as well as southern Gauteng Province. The intermediate morph reported on here has not been recorded previously.

KEYWORDS: Squamata, *Dasypeltis*, egg-eating snakes, colour pattern, reptiles, Free State Province, South Africa.

INTRODUCTION

The widely distributed Afro-Arabian genus *Dasypeltis* Wagler, 1830 includes at least 18 species of egg-eating snakes (Gans 1959; Uetz *et al.* 2025). Of these, the range of the Common Egg-eater *Dasypeltis scabra* (Linnaeus, 1758) stretches from the southernmost part of Africa through most of southern and south-eastern Africa as far north as south-eastern Sudan and central Ethiopia (Auerbach 1988; Broadley 1990; Branch 1998; Bates *et al.* 2014; Bates & Broadley 2018; Bates 2023; Barends *et al.* 2024).

The occurrence of at least two distinct colour morphs of *D. scabra* in South Africa and Zimbabwe was reported by Gans (1959) who examined hundreds of museum specimens of this species. Since then, this phenomenon has been recorded for the same region by several other authors (e.g., Schmidt 1999; Marais 2004; Broadley & Blaylock 2013; Bates *et al.* 2014), and also in Zambia (Broadley *et al.* 2003; Pietersen *et al.* 2021; Barends *et al.* 2024). The dorsal surface of the patterned morph of this species is decorated with a series of dark vertebral ‘saddles’ (e.g., oval, rectangular, more-or-less square or irregular shapes, and sometimes a combination thereof), separated by pale interspaces, alongside which are dark, dorso-ventrally oriented, lateral bars (separated from the saddles). This pattern was referred to as ‘5N’ by Gans (1959). The so-called ‘plain’ morph is pale brown to

grey, sometimes reddish or red-brown in Zimbabwe and Zambia, often with a dark brown vertebral stripe (see Broadley *et al.* 2003; Broadley & Blaylock 2013; Pietersen *et al.* 2021; Barends *et al.* 2024, including Electronic dataset S1). This pattern was referred to as ‘2B’ by Gans (1959). Some Zimbabwean and Zambian snakes are brown or reddish with an intermediate pattern consisting of dark saddles with pale interspaces, and little or no pattern on the flanks (Broadley *et al.* 2003; Broadley & Blaylock 2013; photos 306 & 308; Barends *et al.* 2024).

Here we discuss and illustrate four colour morphs of this common snake, three of which were found on a single farm near Vredefort in the northern Free State, central South Africa. One of these, an ‘intermediate’ morph that differs from the intermediate morphs found in Zimbabwe and Zambia, has not been described until now.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

On 8 August 2020, several Common Egg-eaters (*Dasypeltis scabra*) were collected by the second author on the farm Welverdiend (farm number 851), about 25 km SSW of the town Vredefort, Free State, central South Africa (27.26268°S, 27.23366°E; 2727AD; 1360 m a.s.l.; Fig. 1). The habitat was grassland with scattered clusters of *Vachellia* trees. Large flocks of Red-billed Quelea (*Quelea quelea*) roosted in these

Figure 1: Generalised distribution of the four colour phases/morphs of the Common Egg-eater *Dasypeltis scabra* in South Africa, Lesotho and Eswatini. The farm Welverdiend, SSW of Vredefort, Free State, where the patterned, plain and intermediate morphs occur together, is indicated in yellow. The distribution of the patterned and plain morphs is based on Barends *et al.* (2024); for localities of the striped specimens, see text.

trees, the eggs of which were probably the main source of food for these snakes. Most snakes were of the typical patterned morph, but one had an unusual ‘intermediate’ dorsal pattern. On 11 August 2024, a ‘plain’ snake was also collected on this farm, by J. Marais. The plain and intermediate specimens, as well as a typically patterned snake, were photographed (Fig. 2). All snakes had the typical slender body form of *D. scabra*, with head barely wider than the neck, keeled dorsal scales and a few rows of lateral dorsals reduced, oblique, keeled and serrated (see Gans 1959; Broadley 1990; Bates & Broadley 2018).

An individual of the rare striped morph of *Dasypeltis scabra* (Fig. 2B) from about 10 km south-west of Alberton, Gauteng Province, South Africa (iNaturalist 2025a; Fig. 1) is described below. There are four additional occurrences of striped *D. scabra* in South Africa (Fig. 1): about 3 km south-west of Baragwarath Aerodrome, Gauteng (iNaturalist 2025b), R519 road between Mookgopong and Roedtan, Limpopo (Leonard 2016), Blue Horizon Bay, Eastern Cape (O’Connor 2021), and Gqeberha [Port Elizabeth], Eastern Cape (van Jaarsveld 2021); these are also discussed below. Following the approach of Bates & Stobie (2022), Barends *et al.* (2024) and Stobie & Bates (2025), images retrieved from Facebook have

been saved, but in this case archived in Zenodo to ensure their permanent availability; their DOIs have been added to the corresponding references below.

RESULTS

Four dorsal colour patterns/morphs of *Dasypeltis scabra* have been documented (Fig. 2), with individuals of the typically marked, intermediate and ‘plain’ morphs found on the farm Welverdiend (Figs 2A, C, D). The rare striped morph of *D. scabra* (Fig. 2B; is known from only a few localities (Fig. 1; also Discussion below). Based on the examined specimens (Fig. 2), the four morphs are described as follows.

Typically marked/patterned (‘rhombic’) ‘5N’ morph (Fig. 2A): Overall colour light brown to grey. Large, mostly more-or-less oval, dark brown saddles, separated by narrow whitish interspaces (much narrower than the saddles), with dark bars/bands on the flanks, mostly situated adjacent to the pale interspaces (occasionally additional smaller bands are present alongside the saddles). This dorsal pattern continues onto the base of the tail but the saddles then coalesce into a stripe and the lateral markings become fragmentary. There is a narrow, forward-pointing, V-shaped marking at the back of the head, followed by a bold

Figure 2: Colour patterns in the Common Egg-eater *Dasypeltis scabra* on the farm Welverdiend, 25 km SSW of Vrededorf, Free State, South Africa (A, C, D) and 10 km south-west of Alberton, Gauteng, South Africa (B): (A) typically patterned morph, (B) striped morph, (C) intermediate morph, (D) 'plain' morph with dark vertebral stripe. Photos A, C, D: Luke Kemp; photo B: Eugene Mitton.

but fragmented and less distinctly V-shaped marking on the nape.

Striped morph (Fig. 2B): Similar to the typically marked morph, but the dorsal saddles (except for one on the nape) have coalesced to form a continuous vertebral stripe. Occasionally the shape of saddles is indicated by lateral 'bulging' of the stripe.

Intermediate morph (Fig. 2C): The specimen has an overall pale brown colouration, with vague, somewhat indistinct markings. Saddles are narrow, sometimes barely identifiable (even absent posteriorly), and the interspaces between them are occasionally marked by one, two or a few small cream-white spots or flecks. Lateral dark markings are usually present, but are mostly narrow and often small, fragmentary and indistinct. There are also a few dull dark chevrons on the neck. This morph is intermediate between the typically marked 'rhombic' pattern and the 'plain' form (see photos in Bates *et al.* 2014; Bates & Broadley 2018; Bates 2023; Barends *et al.* 2024). Although the usual colour pattern of snakes may be obscured just prior to ecdysis, the Welverdiend snake shows no signs of being in such condition (e.g., dull skin and/or cloudy, opaque-looking eyes).

'Plain' '2B' morph (Fig. 2D): Pale brown with a darker brown vertebral stripe (mostly four scales wide), a pattern that appears to continue onto the tail. Most of the top of the head is a similar colour to the dark stripe, with a few dark markings at the back of the head and on the neck. The lower flanks where the narrow, oblique, serrated dorsals are situated are grey.

DISCUSSION

Only patterned or 'plain' morphs of *Dasypeltis scabra* have been recorded in South Africa, usually sympatrically, and are restricted to Highveld grasslands in the central and northern parts of the Free State, extending into southern Gauteng (Barends *et al.* 2024). In the Free State, 'plain' snakes represent 9–10% of all *D. scabra* (De Waal 1978; Bates 1992). At some localities the 'plain' morph is frequently encountered: e.g., six out of nine snakes from the farm Quaggaspruit near Lindley (Barends *et al.* 2024, Electronic dataset S1). According to Barends *et al.* (2024), 'plain' or weakly-marked patterns in *Dasypeltis scabra* are probably an adaptation for camouflage in sparsely vegetated grasslands and woodlands.

In Zimbabwe and Zambia, patterned, plain and 'intermediate' colour morphs have been recorded

(Broadley *et al.* 2003; Broadley & Blaylock 2013; Pietersen *et al.* 2021), with instances of sympatry (patterned and plain; patterned and intermediate; patterned, plain and intermediate) (Barends *et al.* 2024). However, the appearance of these snakes is different to the intermediate specimen from the farm Welverdiend near Vrededorf, northern Free State, reported on here. The intermediate snakes from Zimbabwe and Zambia are usually similar to typically marked *D. scabra* in that they have dark dorsal saddles separated by narrow whitish-cream interspaces, but lack dark lateral markings. The Welverdiend snake has an overall brownish appearance (similar to some 'plain' specimens) and mostly smaller and weakly indicated dorsal and lateral markings, and represents a colour variation not previously reported for this species.

Apart from South Africa, Zimbabwe and Zambia, all populations of *D. scabra* from elsewhere in their range reportedly consist of typically patterned individuals. For example, Bates and Broadley (2018) found that all 107 museum specimens of this species from north-east Africa (i.e., northern half of Tanzania, Rwanda, Burundi, Uganda, Kenya, Somalia, Ethiopia, South Sudan and Sudan) were patterned (i.e., no 'plain' or intermediate specimens). This was also the case for Namibia, where all 47 specimens examined by Bates (2023), and others reported on by Barends *et al.* (2024), had the typical marked pattern.

Another rare variation in dorsal colour pattern in *D. scabra* is the striped form (Fig. 2B; also additional records for South Africa listed above; and a snake from Ethiopia, see Bates & Broadley 2018). Such snakes have a continuous, broad, dark vertebral stripe (sometimes wavy in parts, Fig. 2B), as well as dark lateral markings which are usually separated from the vertebral stripe. Although the additional striped snakes are generally similar to Fig. 2B, in one specimen (O'Connor 2021) the markings are 'normal' on the anterior part of the body and the vertebral stripe is especially wavy, whereas a snake found on the R519 road between Mookgopong and Roedtan in the Limpopo Province (Leonard 2016; also Stander 2023: 266) is decidedly ornate with a distinct, narrow, pale brown stripe running through the middle of the dark brown vertebral stripe, the lateral bars are broad and often in contact with, or at least in close proximity to, the dark vertebral band, and numerous small white markings adorn the flanks.

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